

WORLD EXPERIENCE OF LOCAL SELF- GOVERNMENT

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Karakalpak State University Currently has a lot of positive experience in the field of interaction of the population with local self-government bodies in the world experience. But this is not the case in the family. Because the value of the family in Western countries is very different from the value of Eastern peoples. In Europe, the focus is on the person, not the family or neighbors. The mahalla and the family always need the support of the state to fully fulfill their functions as a social institution. After all, these two institutions are, on the one hand, the primary link in the organization of public life, and on the other - a structure that develops, supports and implements civic initiatives. This, in turn, imposes on the State, which is the main governing body of society, the obligation to fully support the activities of these institutions. It is known from world historical experience that the continuity and effectiveness of the activities of any socio-political structures involved in the processes of self-government and self-organization of society cannot be ensured without the participation of the state with the majority of resources.

In the political and legal literature, as well as in international political practice, there is a tradition to express self-government by the term "municipal government". In most countries, the "municipality" is used as a local government structure. The term is often used in legislation, even in the basic law - the Constitution. According to the Russian scientist G.V.Barabashev, the origin and meaning of this term go back to ancient historical periods. The term "municipality" comes from the Latin word "municipium", which usually refers to cities that enjoyed the right of self-government during the republican period of Roman history. Currently, a municipality is an elected city or village government, whereas in the United States only a city government is called a municipality.

According to P. D. Barenboim, the scientific concept of local self-government was first developed in the works of the ideologists of the bourgeois revolution, and its essence and role were connected with the ideas of local government and community self-government. At that time, the principle of electability of local self-government bodies coincided with the idea of representation put forward against feudal absolutism. The theory of the independence of elected municipal bodies, their decentralization in the management of urban and rural communities.

American scientist R.T. According to Burres, throughout the XIX and early XX centuries, i.e. during the period of classical capitalism, the development of local self-government continued in the direction of deviation from the previously proclaimed democratic slogans of equality and freedom. There is a tendency to take State bodies under the control of the State in order to subordinate local interests to national interests.

In the middle of the twentieth century, local self-government partially lost the features of genuine local self-government, once free from the interference of the bureaucratic apparatus of the central government. Some modern authors note that the number of decisions taken by the center is increasing, which places the burden of unconditional implementation of such decisions on local representative bodies. Objectively, this means that local representative bodies become the backbone of public administration, a specific mechanism for implementing the instructions of the central government.

Local self-government and self-government bodies are officially authorities, but they are the powers of the population of administrative-territorial units, defined as territorial communities, and not the state.

From the above considerations, it can be seen that both local government and self-government can be carried out in local administrative-territorial units.

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